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**“Transforming urban and agricultural residues
into high performance biomaterials for green construction”**

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Summary

As the world population increases and develops, pressure on resources required for development becomes more acute. This necessitates improved management of the world's finite resources and improved techniques for processing these resources. This requirement for a more sustainable outlook is pertinent across numerous industrial sectors of which the construction sector is particularly significant since the industry is dependent on many finite resources. In many cases, the use of biobased materials can help contribute to a more sustainable construction sector - but often this is only true if the produced materials can function as required. Biocomposites materials – with beneficial properties of different materials used in the composite but the benefits of a biobased material - can often provide a beneficial solution

The 2-day Biocomposites in Construction Conference (www.BCIC2015.com), which took place at the Society of Chemical Industry in London UK on May 21st and 22nd 2015, highlighted the recent progress, challenges and opportunities associated with use of biocomposites in the construction sector. With both industry experts and researchers presenting, the conference showcased recent development whilst providing a forum for discussion and thus contributing to further future development. In this respect, the conference was successful and as such, we thank all speakers, participants and organisers for their valuable contributions.

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BIOCOMPOSITES IN CONSTRUCTION PERSPECTIVE

Challenges for biocomposites in the construction sector: The ups and downs of research at The BioComposites Centre in the development of bio-based composites for the construction sector

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Abstract:

“The construction industry consumes around 6 tonnes of materials per year for every person living in the UK.” This offers a huge potential for both existing and “new” natural-fibre building materials to enter the market place. However, despite comparable or better technical performance, increased interest and exposure many ‘natural’ products have seen little real growth, merely substitution with other ‘natural’ materials within niche markets.

The presentation given at BCIC2015 shared the experiences of research and development carried out at The BioComposites Centre (BC) into biocomposite materials developed for the construction sector over the last 20 years. It included case studies on the development and research behind certain natural fibre products undertaken at The BioComposites Centre and their subsequent journey to the market place. Examples included:

- the development of hemp fibre insulation and its associated supply chains,
- paper sludge used to develop tile based products
- development of a method to determine the formaldehyde absorption by sheep wool insulation
- development of biobased adhesives for the construction sector
- novel treatment techniques of wood to improve its durability
- Recycling of MDF for construction applications

The presentation also highlighted some of the large multi partner, European, projects BC is involved with including:

- Eco-See, “Eco-innovative, safe and energy efficient wall panels and materials for a healthier indoor environment” A multi partner project lead by Bath University.
- Cost Action FP1303 “Performance of bio-based building materials” This Cost action has been brought about in recognition that performance data for many ‘environmentally friendly’ building materials is lacking as well as suitable comprehensive test methodologies for these products.

Finally, the presentation examined case studies regarding the development and research behind certain natural fibre products, their journey to the market place, how the market has or has not developed and look at what strategies could be developed to help further their mainstream adoption.

Biocomposite construction elements: Experiences from the BioBuild project

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Abstract:

BioBuild was a 3½ year project funded by the European Commission. The aim of the project was to develop new building materials with 50% lower embodied energy when compared to traditional materials by using biocomposites. The BCIC presentation and accompanying paper summarise the key findings of the project and detail the components which were produced.

Compared to traditional materials, composites offer more design freedom and allow weight saving thus reducing the demands on the structure and allowing for shorter build times. There are a number of problems with the use of natural fibres in building materials: fire, moisture and microbial attack. The project addressed all three issues, with mixed success. Biobased resins were also used in conjunction with the natural fibres to produce components which were 100% biobased. Full sized components were made and were subjected to a number of laboratory tests to determine properties such as resistance to wind load, impact damage, thermal and acoustic properties. SBI tests were done on flat panels made of the same materials. Despite the successes of the project (including the JEC Innovation Award for construction), the savings in embodied energy were, in some cases, short of the 50% target. Recommendations for future improvements were made.

Certification and Standardization for Sustainable Construction: Environmental Performance Assessments: LEED and Materials

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Abstract:

About 40% of the UK's energy consumption and carbon emissions come from the way our buildings are lit, heated and used. Small changes in energy efficiency and the way we use each building can have a significant impact in reducing total energy consumption. Several different compulsory and voluntary environmental assessment schemes exist including: Building Regulations Part L, EPC, ESOS, BREEAM, Code for Sustainable Homes and LEED. There are also several tools which are used for performance assessment. The presentation given at BCIC detailed different schemes and tools available - whilst also comparing US-based LEED and UK-based BREEAM and, analysing the main influencers on LEED ratings (Figure 1)

Figure 1. LEED Credit Distribution

The presentation highlighted the importance of:

- complying with up-to-date ISO and EN standards
- publishing product declarations and relevant certificates on the Website:
- Creating links with relevant LEED and BREEAM credits
- Adapting the whole life-cycle process at both product and building level
- Drawing a good roadmap to get your product/material tested and certified

Horizon 2020, is it for you? Funding opportunities for BioBased Materials

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Conference output summary:

Horizon 2020 (H2020) is the biggest EU Research and Innovation programme ever with nearly €80 billion of funding available over 7 years (2014 to 2020). The presentation given at BCIC focussed on explaining the relevant the funding opportunities available as part of the Horizon 2020 funding programme The programme offers funding opportunities across a 3 pillar structure which includes: Excellent Science, Industrial Leadership and Societal Challenges (SC) – each of which contain different topics (Figure 1). The presentation highlighted that SC2 – Bio-economy – Bio-goods and services would likely contain interesting opportunities for biobased research. Other potential opportunities exist in SC5 and ‘Leadership in Enabling and Industrial Technologies’ (LEIT). The BioBased JTI Call supports larger ‘Flagship’ projects with a total eligible budget of €35 million. In addition to this, a €100m funding programme from Biobased Industries (BBI) opens in September. The presentation also detailed key information and tips which may assist in submission of a successful proposal.

Figure 1. H2020- 3 pillar structure

NEW BIOMATERIALS

Bioadhesives and Bioadditives in Construction products

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Conference output summary:

Nature produces a wide variety of glues and additives that outperform synthetic adhesives and additives. This represents an opportunity to search for adhesives and additives with novel interesting properties. This is the reason why several nature concepts are used to search for new bio-alternatives and more healthy products. For instance, in the production of fire retardants FORDEVASA the additive for medium-density fireboard (MDF) and particle boards does not contain boron, heavy metals and halogens. The presentation given at BCIC details these opportunities whilst paying particular attention to current work undertaken by FORESA.

In the case of FORESA, the aim is to bring innovate bioinspired adhesives and additives to the market, by fostering collaboration across disciplines and between different industries and academia through our most innovative projects such as Horizon 2020 which includes an international training network: SUSPOL (Sustainable Organocatalysis and Polymers). Apart from this project, other innovative projects were presented including:

- PAM2WAX (New formulation Emulsion of Vegetable Wax Emulsion for Wood Products). Purpose of the project is to build a "green" product based on sustainable and environmentally friendly raw materials to the environment at the same time as the carbon footprint of the end product is reduced
- SMARTLI (Smart Technologies for the Conversion of Industrial Lignins into Sustainable Materials) that develops technologies for the use of technical lignin as raw materials for biomaterials and demonstrating its industrial feasibility. Technical lignins included in the study are kraft lignin, lignosulfonates and bleaching effluents, representing all types of sources of abundant lignin.
- WOODZYME (Use of enzymes as New Waterproofing Treatment in Wood products) that Deals with the application of enzymes in the panel boards industry. The aim is to bond hydrophobic compounds to the wood lignocellulose surface in a covalent way using oxidase enzymes (specifically laccase) to improve the water resistance (and as consequence fungal resistance).

Advanced 2nd Generation Biorefinery

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Conference output summary:

Currently, the use of renewable resources is a strategic alternative to fossil fuels, with biomass a sustainable solution with several benefits:

- Production capacity;
- Wide availability;
- Ability to be stored and transported;
- CO₂ neutrality;
- High energy content & use as a building block for chemistry;

Depending on the source of the biomass there are different types of biobased products. First-generation or 1G - which utilise agricultural food products as feedstock have been successfully commercialised, yet there is a debate about the use of agricultural lands due to the direct competition with both animal and human food (fuel products such as bioethanol usually use corn and/or sugar beets as feedstock). On the other hand, current two-generation (2G) biorefining processes are inefficient and uneconomic. A 2G biorefinery often uses highly destructive processes (mainly steam explosion) which leads to lower valuable product yields and low purity products. The presentation given at BCIC details the CIMV's advanced lignocellulosic biorefinery concept which is based on:

- Fractionation of non-food biomass into different parts: cellulose, a polymer of glucose; hemicellulose, amorphous polymer of C5 sugars mainly xylose; and lignin, a regular polymer of phenolic monomers.
- The valorisation of all overall inputs, whilst maintaining a low water consumption with a solvent recycling and minimisation of waste production.
- Efficient technology. Using technologies that allows the maximum production of the primary product.
- Maximum monetization of the lignin fraction.

Figure 1 shows how 1 tonne of biomass is transform to different products using the CIMV process.

Additional value is realised in the process by converting primary into more valuable secondary and then tertiary products. Cellulose is converted into glucose syrup through cellulose hydrolysis. The conversion achieved is very high, more than 90 % in 30 hours with a glucose solution above 200 g/ kg of glucose.

From glucose syrup, several products are obtainable. Through isomerisation, glucose is converted into fructose. On the other hand, glucose is converted into ethanol through fermentation,

Another primary product is sugar syrup, which in this case it is C5 sugar syrup. In Figure 2 is represented the different fractions that are possible to obtain from wheat straw C5 syrup. It is important to highlight that the composition depends on the feedstock.

The final primary product is biolignin. This compound could be obtained with a high purity, which means above 91 % in acid insoluble lignin (AIL) plus acid soluble lignin (ASL), and the rest in a content of residual hemicelluloses (5 %) and ashes (1.5 %).

Figure 1. Transformation of biomass into different products

Figure 2. Purification of wheat straw C5

High value-added chemicals and bioresins from algae biorefineries

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Abstract:

BISIGODOS project, a European funded project (FP7/2007-2013) under grant agreement n° [613680], aims to address the production of valuable algae derived chemicals, amino acids and high added-value bio-resins starting from algae biomass fed directly with CO₂ from industrial emissions (cement, steel factory, thermal power plants, etc.) as a cost-effective and renewable raw material. The process is assisted by solar radiation, nutrients and sea water microalgae. This approach is based on the technology developed by the Partner Biofuel Systems (BFS) to produce bio-oil. The presentation gave details of the different partners and concepts of the BISIGODOS project.

The BISIGODOS consortium brings together a wealth of expertise and resources within the areas of:

- Microalgae and photo-bioreactors production and optimization
- Manufacture of amino acids for food products
- Production of conductive polymer coatings
- Bio-resin development for water-based inks
- Bio-surfactants production and bio-PU adhesives manufacturing End-users in the food, flexible packaging, hair care, metal industry and paints products.

The presence of main actors in the whole value chain demonstrates the critical mass of complimentary resources that will enable the BISIGODOS project to achieve its targeted industrial, scientific and societal breakthroughs and commercial success.

To develop these new technologies, the project adopts several innovative approaches:

- New algae strains production optimization and CO₂ energetic balance improvement.
- Optimization of photo-bioreactors. Reduction up to 65% of CO₂ emissions in industrial plants to produce high added value products.
- Study and adaptation of separation of algae components based on hybrid technologies.
- Production of algae derived chemicals for surfactants applications and amino acids for food applications.
- Obtention of a broad range of amino acids and protein hydrolyzates products.
- Production of bio-based resins from algae based fatty acids and bio-oil aromatic moieties.

IMPROVED BIOFIBRES

Overview of cellulose nanofibers production

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Abstract:

During the last three decades, a new cellulose-derived nanomaterial has gained interest as biobased reinforcing material for polymer composites, as rheology modifier, as paper strengthener or building block for porous functional materials. Mostly pristine cellulose pulps were employed so far for its production. However, recent research projects are focusing on obtaining nanocellulose from residues to produce added-value products.

In this presentation, an introduction to different types of nanocelluloses such as Bacterial Cellulose, Cellulose Nanocrystals and Nanofibrillated Cellulose was given, followed by an overview of their emerging market and interests by research institutions and industry. Secondly a more detailed description of Nanofibrillated Cellulose (NFC) structure, properties and isolation methods is provided.

Within the frame of the European project INNOBITE, the possibility of isolating NFC from agricultural and industrial wastes was investigated. Wheat straw residue from a biorefinery plant (WS) and newspapers (NP) from a recycling plant were employed as source of cellulose fibres. They were turned into NFC (Figure 1) through a grinding process carried out in water medium. A reference pristine cellulose pulp from softwood (ECF) was utilized as control material.

The fibrillation quality of the processed waste materials was investigated by SEM microscopy and nitrogen adsorption as well as mechanical testing of randomly distributed nanofibers films in tensile mode. The energy needed for the fibrillation process was recorded upon grinding. Results show that it is possible to obtain NFC from the aforementioned wastes at an acceptable quality level (E modulus between 6 and 8 GPa) and with energy consumption comparable with the one of the reference material (6.75 kWh/kg dry mass for NP, 5.75 kWh/kg dry mass for WS and 5.25 kWh/kg dry mass for ECF).

Figure 1. NFC produced from Newspapers (NP), wheat straw (WS) and cellulose pulp (ECF) prepared by grinding

Nanocellulose applications

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Abstract:

The interest in Cellulose Nanofibers increased exponentially during the last decade. A lot of research groups world-wide are developing new materials that could be used in bio-medical, packaging, electronic, filtering, cosmetic, and automotive applications, e.g. Some of the materials are close to implementation in industry and several companies, especially in US, Canada, Northern Europe and Japan already claim production capacities of cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) or cellulose nanofibrils (CNF) in ton scale. However, a straightforward material supply with marketable prices is still not given.

Recently, up-scaling activities of pristine (and maybe later also functionalized CNF) were also initiated in Switzerland to accelerate the market entry of materials developed between companies and research institutions.

The presentation will give an overview on nanocellulose based material developments at Empa in Switzerland. Here, research focuses on foams and films for gas capture, oil/water separation, thermal insulation, filtration, packaging, or coatings 1-7. Figure 1 summarizes the main uses of CNF as building block in these functional materials towards the use of appropriate chemical functionalization pathways.

Figure 1. Scheme summarizing nanocellulose based material developments at Empa, Switzerland

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Superhydrophobic cellulose fibres to improve the durability of biocomposites

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Abstract:

From the most basic to the most advanced use, cellulose seems always to be one step ahead of any other material, be it natural or synthetic. Besides being the most abundant biopolymer on earth, as well as being renewable, biodegradable and carbon-neutral, cellulose shows a combination of unique properties which make it a very valuable raw material. In the building of a new sustainable world, resource-efficiency must be a fundamental concept and, in that direction, promoting the use of cellulose fibres, as opposed to their dissolution via chemical or physical intensive treatments, not only makes sense for economic and ecologic reasons but should be a priority in order to get the most of the vast potential of such highly-engineered structures. One example is the presence of a hollow interior (lumen), which directly provides effective insulation and reduced density but also opens the possibility to use fibres as compartments to carry other substances.

From the point of view of advanced materials, cellulose hydrophilic character is the major responsible for most of its limitations, especially for its limited use in polymeric formulations (Biocomposites). Accordingly, intensive research has been done in the last decades to change or at least minimize such characteristic but most attempts have failed to provide durable hydrophobicity. Based on the combination of old knowledge and recent findings, a new highly efficient approach for cellulose hydrophobization has been developed (Tejado et al., 2014), which for the first time results in totally hydrophobic and durable cellulose fibres. Such innovation, based on (i) preventing hornification upon drying and (ii) carrying out a surface polymerization via a gas-phase reaction, gives rise to a radically novel fibre product exhibiting spectacular properties (Figure 1), such as a paper with negative hygro-expansion coefficient i.e. which expands upon drying (Chen et al. 2015). The presentation given at the BCIC2015 International Conference described in detail this new methodology as well as the physical phenomena related to it (Figure 2) and the potential that it has in bioconstruction applications.

Figure 1. Hydrophobized cellulose fibres in contact with a drop of water.

Figure 2. Illustrative example of the physical phenomena governing the behaviour of hydrophobized cellulose fibres: partial engulfment is thermodynamically preferred even at high contact angles i.e. high hydrophobic character.

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NEW BIOCOMPOSITES

Foam forming – a new way to produce biobased construction materials

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Abstract:

Foam(-laid) forming technology can be used to create new type of products from biobased materials. This wet process can handle exceptionally wide scale of raw materials. The main benefit of foam forming comes from clearly improved fibre uniformity in the materials. Foam forming technology has been studied already in 1970's but implemented in some extent only in nonwoven and tissue industry. VTT started laboratory-scale foam forming studies in 2008. The main research area is in paper and packaging board applications but research has expanded into fibre based products outside papermaking industry, including construction materials.

In foam forming fibres and other raw materials are mixed with aqueous wet foam instead of water. The foam consists of water, foaming agent and air. Typical air content in the foam is 30 – 70 % and a typical bubble diameter is 100 µm. Fibres and other particles are "frozen" in their dispersed state in the bubble pockets. The air bubbles prevent fibre flocculation. Foam forming allows the utilization of raw materials from centimetre-long fibres to nanoscale particles, even materials lighter than water. It is possible to produce highly porous, low density fibre structures as well as layered products.

Foam forming has been demonstrated in the production of thermal insulation materials, acoustic panels, building boards and natural fibre composites. In composite manufacture the mixture of fibres and ground polymer granulates (alternatively polymer fibres) can be foam formed and compression molded into rigid plates. This has been demonstrated by preparing thermoplastic composites with lignin and softwood kraft, Figure 1. The foam formed thermal insulation material from 100% natural fibres is semi-rigid with similar thermal conductivity values compared to commercial mineral wool, EPS and XPS products. Low density open pore fibre materials can be used as sound absorbers, especially in applications where lightness of the material is a benefit. In building boards, light fibre-based materials can be produced with high material strength.

Figure 1. Stress-strain curves of thermoplastic composite of lignin and softwood kraft prepared by combining foam forming and compression molding. The material strength is compared to materials prepared by injection moulding (marked with "i"). TPL100= 100% lignin, TPL70= 70% lignin etc.

Almond shell based polymers composites

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Abstract:

Spain is the second largest producer of almonds worldwide, after USA, with 12% of the production rate, whereas Europe produces about 165,000 metric tons. The almond shell that is removed accounts for 60% of the full almond and traditionally this waste has been mainly used as heating fuel, or in other occasions this is just discarded, being landfills its final destination.

In order to follow the strategy on resource efficiency of the European Union for 2020, AIJU has been working for the last ten years in a research line regarding the introduction of natural fillers (almond and nut shell, sawdust, cellulose fibres...) in polymers addressed to different industrial sectors such as the automotive, toys and furniture industries. The different projects demonstrated the possibility of developing new plastic compounds containing almond shell in proportions of up to 45% that can be processed by conventional techniques such as extrusion, injection moulding, rotational moulding and even for Additive manufacturing technologies, as laser sintering. Some colour additives are also introduced to obtain commercial masterbatches, both biodegradable (Mastalmond project) and non-biodegradable (Naturmaster project) with good results.

Some of the main results obtained by introducing almond shell in different plastic matrixes for injection moulding are presented in the paper associated with this abstract and the presentation given at BCIC. Almond shell-filled biodegradable polymers (PLA, PHB and a starch-based polymer) and non-biodegradable polymers (HDPE, PP, HIPS) formulations were developed and their mechanical properties determined.

The visual appearance of the products obtained was similar to wood, with the advantage that these composite materials can be transformed without modifying the plastic production lines. In general, by increasing the almond shell content in the compound the elasticity modulus of the polymers, hardness and viscosity increase and the impact strength decreases, property that can be improved by decreasing the size of the particles of almond shell and by reconciling the interface polymer-matrix with chemical surface treatments. Comparing the different polymers, the PS and PHB models are the most affected by the introduction of fibre; however, due to their intrinsic characteristics, the biodegradable nature of the polymer is not a determining factor in the final mechanical properties or the processing.

Finally, the optimum formulations have been validated in industrial children's and furniture injected products. Life Cycle Assessment is currently being carried out to obtain the environmental profile of new biodegradable almond shell masterbatches.

The incorporation of this lignocellulosic filler, a renewable natural resource, in plastics formulations has good prospects from the technical, environmental and economic standpoint and the results achieved could be extended to other industrial sectors such as construction, automotive industry, packaging, footwear and other consumer products, etc.

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Light weight biocomposites for construction sector

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Conference Output Summary:

Polymer foams are found virtually everywhere in our modern world and are used in a wide variety of applications such as disposable packaging, the cushioning of furniture and insulation material. The reason polymer foams are so widely used is that they have a lot of advantageous properties. The foaming reduces the material usage and the final product weight, as a consequence, the cost is reduced as well since more energy is saved in transportation where lighter vehicles consume less fuel. In addition, foaming improves impact resistance, ductility and fatigue apart from improving the thermal and acoustic properties as well due to the thermal insulation that it provides which saves heating and cooling energy. Foams present a wide range of applications due to their versatility. They offer the possibility to tailor materials according to need. The density can be high, medium or low. The cell density can be designed to be conventional, fine-celled, microcellular or nanocellular). And the cell structure can be either closed or open.

Foaming of biocomposites creates new opportunities by combining the advantages of plastic foams and the characteristics of wood fibres such as high strength and stiffness, non-abrasiveness, and easy availability. Besides, light-weight and lower material and energy requirements, the impact strength and ductility of wood based composites can be significantly improved by creating a micro-cellular foam structures.

The presentation given at BCIC focused on describing the extrusion of foamed bio-based thermoplastics which are being developed as a core for an internal insulation board. In the context of OSIRYS Project: Safe, energy-efficient and affordable new eco-innovative materials for building envelopes and/or partitions to provide a healthier indoor environment an interior multilayer structure is being developed by VTT. The multilayer structure is created from light foam biocomposite with light-weight, and excellent mechanical, thermal insulation and sound absorption and insulation properties. The research has up to now focused on the optimisation of foam and process parameters in lab-scale extrusion foaming, and in initial trials using a pilot-scale tandem extrusion line. In the OSIRYS project, the extraction of foamed lignin-based biocomposites for insulation has been studied. The figure below shows the effect of die temperature on cell structure for a lignin based thermoplastic material without fibres and using CO₂ as a blowing agent.

Figure 4. The effect of die temperature on cell structure

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Lignin-based biocomposites – Applications and new developments

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Abstract:

Tecnaro develops, produces and markets biopolymer composites and blends. The portfolio includes “Liquid Wood” ARBOFORM®, Wood Plastic or Natural Fibre reinforced Composites ARBOFILL® and Biopolymer Compound ARBOBLEND®. ARBOFORM® and ARBOBLEND® consist of biopolymers like the wood constituent lignin or of lignin derivatives and/or other biopolymers like Polylactic Acid, Polyhydroxyalkanoates, biobased Polyamides and Polyolefins, etc. used as a binder for natural and other (bio-based) fibres.

The raw material lignin is second only to cellulose as the most abundant natural polymer. It is a by-product from pulp and paper industry. Annually more than 50 million tons are directly burnt. Tecnaro lignin as a component in thermoplastic biomaterials and received several awards related to this sustainable innovation: Diesel Award, European Inventor Award, Deutscher Industriepreis (German Industry Award) 2009, Werkbund label 2008, VR Innovationspreis (Innovation Award of VR Bank) 2007, Golden Euromold Award, etc. The presentation given at BCIC2015 detailed properties and various applications of ARBOFORM.

Figure 1. ARBOFORM pellets

NEW PRODUCTS

The development of a bio-based ultra-light particleboard

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Abstract:

Wood-based particleboard represent an important group of materials for the construction and furniture sectors. Driven by the rising price of raw materials, besides the growing demand for light boards for interior construction, packaging and flat-pack furniture, manufacturers are trying to make panel materials significantly lighter in weight. The research work is focusing on a new, cost-efficient one-step production processes for sandwich panels with wood chip based top layers originally developed at Hamburg University. The emphases of the currently running research project are: (a) to develop a bio-based foam precursor that can be applied as granulate; (b) to adapt the one-step process to the new core-layer material; and (c) to perform an ecological assessment to compare different core layer materials. The presentation gave an overview of the research work, which is being has been undertaken within a cooperation of Bern University of Applied Sciences (BFH), École polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL) and Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology (EMPA).

Figure 1

Decorative laminates – Wood fibre based biocomposites

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Abstract:

The market for biocomposites continues to grow, and is expected to have a significant share of various applications, having also a major potential in construction. Laminates are widely used as construction elements, including interior panels and flooring. High Pressure Laminates (HPL) are a type of modern flooring, which are manufactured by pressing e.g. thermoset-impregnated wood fibre-based layers together under high pressure and heat. The result is a wood fibre reinforced plastic composite with several distinct functionalities due to adequate choices of fibre grades, thermoset resin grades, process conditions and manufacturing equipment. When used in applications such as flooring or in kitchen worktops the laminates need to be persistent to abrasion, scratch, staining and burns. For development of a given strength, appearance and surface topography of a laminate, the process conditions during pressing, the choice of press plate and the choice of materials and structure of the resin-impregnated wood fibre-based layers are essential. Detailed understanding of the structures of these layers is thus important for improving specific characteristics of laminates. The presented work included decorative laminate samples having the same structural composition, but differing with respect to the surface perception. A detailed structural and mechanical characterisation has been performed, which reveals the structural composition and its effect on the quality perception and mechanical performance. This insight to the internal architecture of these composite materials will be most valuable for further development of superior and modern laminate solutions, thus opening for new market opportunities for the pulp and paper industry.

A major part of laminate flooring is composed of wood fibres. *Photo: PFI.*

Figure 1

Fire safety for bio-based green building materials

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Abstract:

Bio-based building products have a very long history, e.g. as timber structural members. Combustibility was the main reason why bio-based building materials were banned from many applications. When performance based design (PBD) became possible many building regulations opened the market for bio-based building products. Modern living offers attractive, flexible buildings and aims for cost efficient building techniques. Sustainability of building products became an issue. Consumers demand renewable products; however the Fire Safety of the end-product has to remain on a high level. Requirements of fire performance for construction elements depend on the specific area where the product is allocated and the use of the building. Public concurrence buildings require higher safety against fire events and smog density and toxicity has become of major concern.

In this context, Bio based sustainable materials require environmental friendly flame retardant solutions. Halogenated flame retardants were used widely in the past, but current development is towards alternative fire safety solutions, and R&D is almost universally towards PIN flame retardants (phosphorous, inorganic and nitrogen based FR). PIN flame retardants act through a range of mechanisms, including in the condensed phase (acting on the polymer), creating a protective layer or radiation shield at the polymer-fire interface (char, intumescence, inorganic glass) or reacting with the polymer to prevent flammable breakdown products being generated, and also acting in the gas phase to inhibit the flame. The selection of most appropriate PIN system for bio-based materials is a question to solve case by case but What about bio-sourced PIN flame retardants? Chitosan, lignin, cellulose, starch, cardanol derivatives are being developed for fire retardant protection. The presentation given at the BCIC2015 International Conference examined the potential application and implications of conventional and bio-based flame retardants

Reduced fuel production by condensed phase action for Low Fire Risk and Low Fire Hazard

Heat Induced Surface Protection

Figure 1